

BRILL

MNEMOSYNE 78 (2025) 653-682

MNEMOSYNE
A Journal
of
Classical Studies
brill.com/mnem

The Stoic Apollophanes of Antioch

Christian Vassallo

Università degli Studi di Torino, Torino, Italy

christian.vassallo@unito.it

Received 24 July 2023 | Accepted 20 September 2023 |

Published online 4 July 2025

Abstract

This paper provides a new edition of the extant testimonies to the Stoic Apollophanes of Antioch (3rd century BCE), a close follower of Aristo of Chios, and a full overview of his *bios* and doctrine as it emerges also from important new evidence not taken into account by Hans von Arnim in his *Stoicorum Veterum Fragmenta*. It is shown that defining Apollophanes as a ‘heterodox’ Stoic *tout court* does little justice to the complexity of his positions, especially those which distinguish him from his teacher, sometimes in a striking way.

Keywords

Apollophanes of Antioch – Aristo of Chios – sense perception – soul – Stoic ethics and physics

* This research is part of the project ERC-Consolidator Grant 101086695-APATHES (*Assessing Philosophical Authors and Texts from Herculaneum and elsewhere on Early Stoicism: Insights into ancient logic, physics, and ethics towards a new von Arnim*) funded by the European Commission (Horizon Europe Program 2021-2027, Excellent Science). The ultimate version of this paper has also been made possible by the fruitful discussion I had concerning my new edition of Apollophanes at the *Ruprecht-Karls-Universität Heidelberg* on the occasion of the *Gründungsworkshop der GANPH-AG ‘Philosophie im Hellenismus’* (September 14-16, 2023). I am grateful to David Konstan for some useful advice and I dedicate this article to his sweet memory.

1 Introduction

In the sequence about the ‘heterodox’ or ‘dissident’ Stoics (οἱ διενεχθέντες) that we find in Diogenes Laertius’ *Lives* (7.160-167)—viz. Aristo of Chios, Dionysius of Heraclea (nicknamed ‘the Renegade’), and Herillus of Chalcedon¹—the name of Apollophanes of Antioch does not appear. The same seems to be the case with Philodemus’ *Index Stoicorum*, large portions of which have been handed down by *PHerc.* 1018.² This absence is also noticeable in the most recent attempts to provide a historical-philosophical reconstruction of the life and thought of the exponents of early Stoicism,³ despite the fact that Hans von Arnim reserved a separate place to Apollophanes in the history of the school. I am referring to five testimonies (*SVF* 1.404-408) which essentially make up an appendix to his edition of the fragments of Aristo⁴—an edition which takes up several pages at the very beginning of the section of the *Stoicorum Veterum Fragmenta* devoted to Zeno of Citium’s disciples (*SVF* 1.333-403).

Diogenes Laertius mentions only two otherwise unknown ‘Aristoneans’, namely Miltiades and Diphilus,⁵ the former of whom may possibly have been Aristo’s son (although this is only a hypothesis).⁶ Apollophanes’ place among the ‘Aristoneans’, however, is sufficiently attested by Athenaeus (T8), who explicitly describes him as a pupil (γνώριμος) of Aristo.⁷ However, as we will shortly see, from the information that can now be put together we are not entitled to make Apollophanes a ‘heterodox’ Stoic who merely lived in the shadow of his teacher, so to speak. Indeed, there is enough evidence to regard him as a philosopher who was not only interested in ethics (like Aristo), but who held somewhat original views in the epistemological and psychological fields. Indeed, certain sources mention Apollophanes in polemical accounts (e.g.

1 On the correctness of this ethnicon, instead of ‘of Carthage’ (accepted by von Arnim), see von der Mühl 1963, 6-9.

2 See Dorandi 1994, 17-19 and Ranocchia 2020, 9-39.

3 See Dorandi 1999, 39-40 and 50-51. Apollophanes is explicitly described as a “philosophe stoïcien hétérodoxe” by Guérard 1989, 296 in his entry for the *Dictionnaire des Philosophes Antiques*, edited by R. Goulet. There is no mention of this in the very brief note on Apollophanes written by von Arnim 1895a for the Pauly/Wissowa, which nevertheless highlights that the figure of Apollophanes cannot be reduced to that of his master (“doch beschränkte er sich nicht, wie sein Lehrer, auf die Ethik, usw.”). On this last fundamental point, see below.

4 1. *Aristo Chius* ~ 1a. *Apollophanes*.

5 Cf. D.L. 7.161 (= Arist. Ch. *SVF* 1.333[1]). On this piece of evidence, cf. below, § 2.

6 See Saal 1852, 8.

7 Concerning this disputed testimony, cf. again below, § 2.

Philodemus⁸) or in more objectively doxographical ones (e.g. Aëtius⁹) concerning Stoic approaches in such fields. The scarcity of sources on Apollophanes in von Arnim's collection and the failure to fully examine new testimonies (particularly some Herculanean passages) dealing with this Stoic philosopher have evidently contributed to the undeserved oblivion surrounding him. The purpose of the present paper is to reverse this trend and to provide the first exhaustive historical-philosophical overview of the figure of Apollophanes in the light of a complete and updated edition of the sources available to us.

2 The Stoicism of Apollophanes of Antioch between 'Heterodoxy' and 'Orthodoxy'

2.1 *Bio-doxography*

We have no precise biographical information on Apollophanes. We can only say that he was born in Antioch, Mesopotamia,¹⁰ at the beginning of the 3rd century BCE. Later, in Athens, he followed Aristo of Chios,¹¹ who, in 262/1 BCE—the year of Zeno's death, which occurred during the archonship of Arrhenides¹²—established himself as a popular lecturer at the Cynosarges, so much so that he came to be regarded as the founder of a new school (αἰρετιστής).¹³ From Philodemus' *On Rhetoric* (T 1¹⁴) we indirectly learn that Apollophanes was a model of the active life, i.e. that he was politically engaged; therefore, he stood as an illustrious exponent of a kind of *bios* that was the absolute opposite of that advocated by the *Kepos*.¹⁵ In some ways, the Philodemian testimony suggests that Apollophanes' activity made him a

8 Cf. T 3 and T 9.

9 Cf. T 5.

10 On this ethnicon, cf. Steph. Byz., s.v. Ἀντιόχεια.

11 Cf. T 8.

12 Cf. Phld. *Sto.*, *PHerc.* 155 + 339, col. 5.9-14 Dorandi.

13 Cf. above, n. 5. There is no reason to doubt that Aristo *consciously* founded a new (Stoic) school, as already suggested by von Arnim 1895b, 957. What is more open to debate is the factor that may have led to this outcome. Probably, it was not personal resentment, but rather Aristo's firm belief that he was proposing the most authentic interpretation of Zeno's doctrine. In this regard, it is difficult to fully subscribe to the idea put forward by Ioppolo 1980, 22 that Diogenes Laertius' testimony, and therefore the idea of a real "split", should not be taken literally. On this point, see also Ranocchia 2007, *passim* and 2020, 104-106, with regard to Phld. *Ind. Sto.*, *PHerc.* 1018, col. 10.11-13.

14 On the ascription of this *scorza* to Book 4 of *On Rhetoric*, see Fimiani 2012, 129-134, esp. 131.

15 On the Epicureans' anti-Stoic polemics with regard to this point, I refer to Roskam 2007. See also Longo Auricchio 2001.

charismatic character, perhaps even outside his school. Philodemus evokes the image of a tower (τὴν ... τύρῃ[σι]ν) in relation to Apolophanes¹⁶ and, in mentioning the figure of a tribune (ἐπι] τοῦ βήματος), he seems to be making an indirect reference to the philosopher's marked oratorical skills—a characteristic he had in common with his teacher, who was known as the 'Siren' on account of his rhetorical prowess.¹⁷ Unfortunately we do not know which and how many offices Apolophanes may have held, in what circumstances he displayed his eloquence, and indeed in what way he participated in the political events of his time.

The number of Apolophanes' works is unknown and the sources only hand down two titles: *Physics* (T 2) and *Aristo* (T 8). The latter treatise is particularly significant because it is connected to the bio-doxographical aspects of this Stoic thinker. The ambiguity of Athenaeus' passage about Apolophanes' works has caused much discussion, giving rise to conflicting theses. In T 8, in particular, we read that both Eratosthenes of Cyrene and Apolophanes, both disciples of Aristo, were the authors of a treatise titled *Aristo*, in which they spoke about their teacher's φιληδονία. Hirzel considered this testimony to be proof of the fact that Apolophanes was a dissident pupil of Aristo.¹⁸ Ioppolo, instead, proposed to consider this piece of news in objective terms, without reading any disparaging intent into it. To support this interpretation, she evoked the analogous information concerning Eratosthenes, suggesting that we interpret Aristo's ethics as a non-radical anti-hedonistic doctrine.¹⁹

Ioppolo's thesis is highly questionable, especially since even in Eratosthenes' case Aristo's debauchery does not appear to be described in a neutral way. Indeed, the image of the perforation of the wall of Pleasure represents a *Verspottung* that clearly betrays a certain resentment, if not a deep sense of disappointment.²⁰ Therefore, I am inclined to re-evaluate Hirzel's thesis and to assign the verb ἐμφανίζω in Athenaeus' testimony a negative meaning ('to denounce', as I prefer to translate, or rather 'to accuse', not simply 'to make

16 On the contrast between these two lifestyles—highlighted by this Herculanean piece of evidence—and on the meaning of Philodemus' quotation of E. *Ph.* 1175-1176 in *PHerc.* 463, fr. 13.11-14, see Longo 1966, 263-265.

17 D.L. 7.160 (= Arist. Ch. *SVF* 1.333[1]).

18 Hirzel 1877-1883, II, 101-102 n. 2 ("Wer aber von der φιληδονία Aristons erzählt hatte, kann nur ein abtrünniger Schüler desselben gewesen sein"), correcting Zeller's more conciliatory interpretation.

19 Ioppolo 1980, 24-25 n. 17, 184-185.

20 A reading of this kind is given by Isnardi Parente 1989, I, 323 n. 113, who, while excluding denigration, nevertheless thinks of a form of blame, both in the case of Eratosthenes and in that of Apolophanes.

clear'). But that is not all. In my opinion the solution to the problem is to be found in the adverb ὕστερον that precedes the quotation from Eratosthenes' *Aristo*. It is quite evident that according to this passage Aristo only devoted himself to φιληδονία at an advanced stage of his life. On closer inspection, even Athenaeus' testimony on Apollophanes suggests a sort of "conversion to pleasure" in Aristo's old age. The reference to Dionysius of Heraclea that immediately follows Apollophanes' "denunciation" of his teacher's φιληδονία (περὶ δὲ Διονυσίου τοῦ Ἡρακλεώτου τί δεῖ καὶ λέγειν;) sounds like a confirmation of this perspective. But evidently this sort of moral "derailment", which was undoubtedly experienced by his closest disciples as a sort of (philosophical) betrayal, occurred in the very last phase of Aristo's life. Hence, it did not erase the memory of Aristo's ethics as a rigid and rigoristic doctrine: an image attested above all by Cicero,²¹ but also, for example, by Clement of Alexandria.²² Although Apollophanes' criticism of Aristo on the ethical level occurred in the later phase of their relationship, it helps to make Apollophanes a very *sui generis* 'Aristonean' even in the field of ethics, despite the strong points of contact between him and his teacher.²³ But this originality will become clearer towards the end of my attempt to delineate this figure on the historical-philosophical level.

2.2 *Logic*

Judging from the sources available to us, the only epistemological principle defended by Aristo, in polemical opposition to the Sceptical Academy (particularly Arcesilaus), would appear to have been that of sensory evidence (ἐνάργεια) and the cataleptic impression.²⁴ His philosophy, however, was inspired by a radical anti-dialectical approach, entailing a focus on ethics alone.²⁵ Long observes that Aristo's anti-dialectical attitude should be read in the light of his tendency to emphasise the Cynical imprinting of Stoicism.²⁶ However, it is reasonable to believe that the three-book treatise *Against the Dialecticians* was directed against dialectic, understood—according to the double definition

21 Arist. Ch. *SVF* 1.367-368. Cf. also *Hort*. fr. 38 Müller (= fr. 44 Ruch = fr. 45 Grilli), missing in *SVF* and mentioned by Ioppolo 1980, 184 n. 33.

22 Arist. Ch. *SVF* 1.370.

23 Cf. below, § 2.4.

24 D.L. 7.162 (= Arist. Ch. *SVF* 1.346).

25 See Ioppolo 2005, 141-149 (on Aristo's theory of perception), esp. 144-145 (on Apollophanes' passage, 145 n. 93) and 149-151 (on Aristo's rejection of dialectic). The scholar (*ibid.*, 63), however, rightly points out that the sources attest to Aristo's interest also in physical topics (for example, the issue of divinity), as well as "aesthetic" ones (especially poetics), although the latter claim is a matter of dispute.

26 Long 1996a, 90.

given by Diogenes Laertius (7.42)—as the ‘science of discoursing correctly on arguments in question-and-answer form’ (ἐπιστήμην οὔσαν ... τοῦ ὀρθῶς διαλέγεσθαι περὶ τὸν ἐν ἐρωτήσει καὶ ἀποκρίσει λόγον), rather than as the ‘science of things true and false and neither true nor false’ (ἐπιστήμην ἀληθῶν καὶ ψευδῶν καὶ οὐδετέρων), since the latter meaning of dialectic was only introduced by Chrysippus.²⁷ It is therefore evident that Apollophanes’ interest in dialectic must be referred to the first kind of dialectic. The fact remains that this interest in dialectic stood in contrast to his teacher’s dismissive attitude towards this field of investigation. Thus, Apollophanes remained faithful to Zeno as regards the structure and partition of philosophy (logic, physics, and ethics) and we have no reason to believe that he ever changed his opinion on this matter.²⁸

The Herculean, most likely Philodemean, treatise *De sensibus* (T 3) suggests that Apollophanes too was a staunch supporter of the principle of evidence. In this sense he was truly ‘Aristonean’. But the other information we have does not allow us to reduce Apollophanes’ Stoicism to the ethical field alone. We are therefore entitled to regard his defence of ἐνάργεια as part of a purely epistemological battle. Apollophanes, however, also pursued—certainly not by chance—physical studies.²⁹ His ‘heterodox’ side, if we exclude the fidelity to Aristo’s doctrine of virtue,³⁰ does not even stand out from a complete disinterest in “logic” in the broad sense of the word, in particular as regards such a complex aspect of the theory of knowledge as analogy (and memory),³¹ attested precisely by *PHerc.* 19/698. Together with col. 19, col. 18 Monet constitutes a thematic section of the treatise devoted to the relationship between sense perception and time. The anonymous Epicurean writer’s criticism of Apollophanes’ theory of the involvement of sense perceptions in analogy

27 The fact remains that, according to the sources available to us, only Sphaerus and Cleanthes, among Zeno’s pupils, wrote logical works (D.L. 7.175 and 178).

28 On the Stoic division of philosophy, see, among others, Hadot 1979, 208–221 and Ierodiakonou 1993. On Aristo’s stance concerning the tripartition of philosophy and his criticism of dialectic, see Ioppolo 1980, 59–69, who draws attention to the fact that the problem is not the division of philosophy as such, but that of the λόγος κατὰ φιλοσοφίαν (which was divided for didactic reasons): Aristo was actually one of those Stoics who transmitted their teaching “jointly”, radicalising Zeno’s idea that philosophy is a unitary whole. On the problem of faithfulness to Zeno in early Stoicism more generally, see Ioppolo 1996.

29 T 2. Cf. below, § 2.3.

30 T 7. Cf. below, § 2.4.

31 It should be noted, however, that, since it is a question of the soul’s memory, Apollophanes’ arguments on the subject also fall within the sphere of physics. But we know that, in the common Stoic view, the three parts of philosophy were closely interwoven (cf. above, n. 28).

should be contextualised precisely by viewing it in relation to this line of reasoning. For the Epicurean author sense perceptions, which are irrational in themselves, cannot be endowed with memory; hence, it is absurd to believe that present sense perceptions, through the process of analogy, can be remembered by past ones and therefore be influenced (or confused) by them.³² From this critique it is clear that Apollophanes advocated a doctrine of memory that somewhat resembles the Platonic theory of recollection,³³ but we are unable to establish to what extent this similarity was a conscious theoretical option.

In this regard, the expression ὑπὸ τοῦ | πιθανοῦ κ[ι]νηθεῖς at lines 4-5 of T 3 remains a riddle. What does it mean that Apollophanes was led by the πιθανόν to ascribe the faculty of memory to sense perceptions and to assume that the latter are involved in the process of analogy? I understand that substantivised adjective as a reference to the “criterion of the probable”, thus rejecting the reading which would lead that term back to the strictly rhetorical-sophistic field.³⁴ This is obviously something different from the πιθανόν that was later adopted in the Sceptical Academy (viz. Carneades). I would argue that the Epicurean author is alluding here to a reasoning developed by Apollophanes in accordance with the principles of his school. In my opinion, he is referring to Zeno of Citium’s doctrine of memory, which defined the latter as a sort of ‘storage of impressions’ (μνήμη θησαυρισμὸς οὐσα φαντασιῶν).³⁵ But the impressions are conveyed to the intellect (νοῦς) precisely by sense perceptions, without which it would be unable to grasp bodies. So the intellect behaves like wax receiving an imprint (τύπωσις).³⁶

Now, the role of impressions in the Stoic doctrine of knowledge could justify the technical meaning of the term πιθανόν in the passage from *PHerc.* 19/698 we are dealing with. Diocles of Magnesia attests that, for the Stoics, an utterance is ‘probable’ when it leads to assent (πιθανὸν δὲ ἐστὶν ἄξιωμα τὸ ἄγον εἰς συγκατάθεσιν).³⁷ In Stoic epistemology, impressions are classified into two

32 See Monet 1996, 56 and 65. It is interesting to note the affinities between many of these arguments and Philodemus’ *On Signs*, Book 3 (*PHerc.* 1065), to which I refer below (app. crit. *ad* T 3) in relation to all those passages in which the concepts of analogy (col. XXXVII.14; fr. III.1, 4 De Lacy) and evidence (cols. VII.21; XV.26, 28; XXII.7 De Lacy) occur.

33 Longo 1966, 269.

34 This is the interpretation adopted by Longo 1966, 269, who was probably influenced by her wrong reading ἡδυνθεῖς.

35 *SVF* 1.64. On the reference to Zeno in this Sextus Empiricus’ passage (*Adv. math.* 7.373), see Pearson 1891, 67-68.

36 *SVF* 2.55-58.

37 D.L. 7.75 (= *SVF* 2.201[1]).

groups, persuasive (*πιθαναί*) and non-persuasive (*ἀπιθανοί*): the former are those impressions that produce an incisive action on the soul, the latter those that distance us from assent. Both types of impressions can be either true or false. The true ones can be cataleptic or non-cataleptic. Non-cataleptic impressions are affected by the state in which the perceiver finds himself (for example, madness in the case of a madman). Cataleptic impressions, on the other hand, are imprinted on the soul starting from a truly existing reality, meaning that they perfectly correspond to their external objects and, starting from sense perceptions, induce us to assent.³⁸

2.3 *Physics*

As already mentioned in § 2.1, we know that Apollonphanes dealt with physics and that he devoted a special treatise to this subject, in which—among other topics—he certainly examined the concept of vacuum (T 2). This fundamental theme in Stoic physics had already been a focus of analysis for Zeno of Citium, according to whom vacuum consists in the absence of a body. Together with place, time, and *lekta*, vacuum is one of the ‘incorporeals’³⁹ and is characterised by being continuous, infinite, separated from the cosmos, outside the sky (i.e. extending around it), and therefore outside of the ‘whole’.⁴⁰ We have no evidence to suggest that Apollonphanes introduced substantial innovations to these foundations of the Stoic theory of vacuum, which Chrysippus later explored in a more systematic manner.⁴¹

The other line of physical studies that Apollonphanes certainly pursued is related to the nature and functions of the soul. Indeed, we may suppose that psychology was one of the subjects in which Apollonphanes was most interested. Aëtius (T 5) attests that the Stoics in general considered the soul to consist of eight parts (*μέρη*):⁴² the five parts pertaining to sensory perceptions

38 S.E. *M.* 7.242 (= *SVF* 2.65). See, among others, Frede 1999, 316–321; on the complex notion of *ἀσθησις* in early Stoicism, see Rubarth (2004) 322–330.

39 S.E. *M.* 10.218 (= *SVF* 2.331). On the Stoic concepts of place and vacuum, see LS 49 A–J, Algra 1995, 261–339, Alessandrelli 2014, and Tieleman 2014; on the problem of time, LS 51 A–H and Goldschmidt 2006⁴; on the *lekta*, LS 33 A–q, Alessandrelli 2013, and Bronowski 2019. On the Stoic incorporeals in general, see now de Harven 2025, 255–444.

40 *SVF* 1.94–96.

41 *SVF* 2.424–425; 428; 477[1]; 502–505[1]; 528; 535; 538–539; 541; 542–543; 545–546; 552; 557; 619.

42 On the basis of the criterion he had specified in the *Praefatio* to his *Stoicorum Veterum Fragmenta* (I, IX–X), von Arnim assigned this *doxa* to Chrysippus (*SVF* 2.827). Note that, in ch. 4.4 of Aëtius’ compendium, the position of the two Stoic *doxai* (§§. 4–5) falls perfectly in the middle: the first three *doxai* refer to Pythagoras/Plato (§. 1), Xenocrates (§. 2), and Aristotle (§. 3); the last three to the Pythagoreans (§. 6), Democritus/Epicurus (§. 7), and Democritus (§. 8).

(sight, hearing, smell, taste, and touch); the phonetic part (the one related to the voice); the spermatic part (the one related to reproduction); and, finally, the regent part, that is to say the main part of the soul from which all the others branch off (Aëtius uses the metaphor of the octopus and its tentacles). Apollophanes instead apparently proposed a division into nine parts.⁴³ If, as I believe, this is plausible (see below), then Apollophanes' *doxa* can be regarded as the expression of a 'heterodox' thesis concerning this fundamental aspect of Stoic psychology, not least on account of the very position it occupies in Aëtius' chapter. As a matter of fact, Apollophanes' opinion is the only one attributed to a specific Stoic. However, Aëtius does not say which part of the soul Apollophanes identified as the ninth, and it can be assumed that he also accepted the other eight indicated in the previous *doxa*. The problem is to understand what meaning the concept of "part (of the soul)" had in his psychological doctrine.

Even before this issue, the question emerges of the relationship between Aëtius' testimony and the far more detailed one from Tertullian's *De anima* (T 6). These two pieces of evidence differ in terms of their structure. For example, Aëtius' text lacks the ascending trend in the number of parts of the soul that we find in the Church Father.⁴⁴ However, as regards the shared *doxa* on Apollophanes, it is perfectly possible that both Aëtius and Tertullian depended on a common doxographical source. Following Diels' authoritative opinion, Waszink claimed that Tertullian's source was Soranus' treatise *On the Soul* (Περὶ ψυχῆς).⁴⁵ But this is not the place to delve into such aspects of the *Quellenforschung*. What is more interesting for our purposes is the fact that from Tertullian's passage it emerges that it makes little sense to speak of Stoic 'heterodoxy' with regard to the "mereology" of the soul, since, from Zeno of Citium to Posidonius, there was never a unity of views on this point within the Stoic school: Zeno identified three parts, Apollophanes nine, Chrysippus eight, and other unspecified Stoics twelve; finally, as far as Middle Stoicism

43 It should be recalled, however, that Aët. 4.4.5 Mansfeld/Runia stems from a supplement which Wachsmuth made to the text of Stobaeus. In making this choice, Wachsmuth followed Elter 1880, 40. See Mansfeld/Runia 2020, I, 61 n. 245; III, 1452. In the Arabic translation of Aëtius (Daiber 1980, 192-193) we only find the passage about the Stoics, not the one about Apollophanes. On the Stoic "octopoid" soul (and its Peripatetic background), see Rapp 2023.

44 Mansfeld/Runia 2020, III, 1455.

45 Waszink 2010, 21*-44*, esp. 30*-34*, who, using the terminology coined by Diels for the reconstruction of Aëtius' sources, claimed that Soranus (*De an.* fr. 10 Podolak) had in turn drawn that information from the *Vetusta Placita* through the probable intermediation of Aenesidemus. See also Mansfeld/Runia 2020, III, 1462.

is concerned, the division ranges from the six parts theorised by Panaetius to the fourteen posited by Posidonius, who later increased them to seventeen.⁴⁶ Tertullian, however, warns us that psychological divisions do not refer so much to *partes* (in Greek, μέρη) as to *vires et efficaciae et operae*, viz. ‘faculties’ or ‘powers’ (in Greek, δυνάμεις). Unfortunately, the surviving testimonies on Stoic psychology are often conflicting with regard to the relationship between ‘parts’ and ‘faculties’ or ‘powers’. Sextus Empiricus, for example, seems to combine the two notions and lead them both back to the opposition between rational (λογικόν) and irrational (ἄλογον).⁴⁷ There are undoubtedly certain authors, such as Diogenes Laertius, Porphyry, and Philo of Alexandria, who speak exclusively of ‘parts’: they too enumerate eight, according to the same criteria followed by Aëtius (i.e. the five senses, phonation, reproduction, and reason).⁴⁸ But, as Inwood observes, probably “the most important partition of the soul in standard Stoic theory is not a division into parts at all, but a distinction of powers within one part”, namely the regent part of the soul.⁴⁹ As is well known, this is confirmed above all by an excerpt from Iamblichus’ treatise *On the Soul* handed down by Stobaeus.⁵⁰ among other things, Iamblichus states that while it is true that the soul is divided into eight ‘parts’ (ὀκταμερῆ), its ‘faculties’ (δυνάμεις) are many more.⁵¹ Although the matter remains unclear, it is possible to infer that the ‘parts’ are the sections into which the soul is spatially divided and which allow it to exercise its ‘faculties’, i.e. its substantial qualities.

To return to Aëtius’ report, a working hypothesis might be that the doxographer generally defines the parts of the soul as μέρη. But this does not exclude that Apollonphanes’ position was only apparently ‘heterodox’ in comparison to the original tripartition of the soul in Zeno. Most probably Apollonphanes

46 On this point, see Schindler 1934; on Panaetius’ stance (test. 128 Alesse), Alesse 1994, 194-217, esp. 202-203 n. 77; on Posidonius (fr. 147 Edelstein/Kidd), Kidd 1988, 544-548.

47 S.E. M. 7.359 (= SVF 2.849[2]). Note that even before this passage, *ibid.* 7.234, Sextus credits the Stoics with assigning a double meaning to the soul, as that which holds together the compound in its entirety (τό τε συνέχον τήν ὅλην σύγκρισιν) and as that which refers to the regent part *tout court* (κατ’ ἰδίαν τὸ ἡγεμονικόν). See Inwood 2014, 67-68, who also refers to D.L. 7.138-139.

48 D.L. 7.110, 157 (= SVF 2.828); Porph. *De an.* ap. Stob. 1.49.25a6-11, p. 350 Wachsmuth (= SVF 2.830); Phil. Al. *Quaest. et solut. in Gen.* 1.75 *et alibi* (= SVF 2.832-833).

49 Inwood 2014, 70.

50 Stob. 1.49.33-34, pp. 367-369 Wachsmuth (= *partim* SVF 1.142; 2.826, 831), on which see Inwood 2014, 70-74. The question becomes more complicated in the case of authors such as Galen, who in *De placitis Hippocratis et Platonis* states that according to Chrysippus the soul is an entity comprising τὸ ἄλογον and τὸ λογιζόμενον (2.7, p. 156.6-9 De Lacy = SVF 2.888), but elsewhere more generically speaks of ἐνέργεια (2.4, p. 128.5-6 De Lacy = SVF 2.893[2]) or δυνάμεις (3.7, p. 214.1-3 = SVF 2.900[2]).

51 In particular, in the regent part impression (φαντασία), assent (συγκατάθεσις), appetite (ὄρμη), and reason (λόγος) should be singled out. On this point, see Long 1996b, 245.

referred precisely to the ‘faculties’ (δυνάμεις) of the regent part rather than to the ‘parts’ (of the soul) in the strict sense.⁵²

2.4 *Ethics*

Let us move on to ethics. Athenaeus’ testimony on pleasure (T 8) has already been discussed. We should now reflect on the two sources that allow us to say something about Apollophanes’ conception of virtue and death. It is best to start with the first problem. Diogenes Laertius (T 7) attests that Apollophanes was a supporter of the uniqueness of virtue. According to Zeller, the doctrine of the one virtue, which Apollophanes identifies as φρόνησις, is an essentially Aristonean position.⁵³ But this thesis was already corrected by Hirzel, who hypothesised that Apollophanes’ view of this issue was rather closer to Zeno’s.⁵⁴ In any case, according to the *doxai* on the subject that Diogenes Laertius attributes to the other Stoics before the testimony on Apollophanes, the latter certainly disagreed with, and probably attacked, the stance held by his contemporary Cleanthes. Indeed, Diogenes says that Cleanthes,⁵⁵ along with Chrysippus⁵⁶ and Antipater,⁵⁷ was among those who posited more than four virtues.⁵⁸

Finally, Apollophanes’ ethical reflection also extended to the topic of death. This must have been a central aspect of his philosophy, for otherwise it would be difficult to explain why Philodemus chose Apollophanes as the target of his polemic when seeking to criticise the Stoic school. To better contextualise the passage, in T 9 I have decided to include the two columns from Book 4 of Philodemus’ *On Death* that follow the very fragmentary one in which Apollophanes’ name appears (col. 84 Delattre). Basing myself on Delattre’s new edition, I believe that the Epicurean philosopher’s polemical arguments provide sufficient elements to infer *e contrario* what Apollophanes *supposedly* thought about death and the ethical questions surrounding it.

According to some scholars, Philodemus is here contesting the idea that one can die without pain at the moment of separation of the soul from the body.⁵⁹ The new reconstruction of the passage suggests that this was rather the position

52 According to Isnardi Parente 1989, I, 322 n. 111—who also refers to T 3—, “forse Apollifane considerava la memoria una vera e propria parte a sé stante dell’anima o un senso distinto dagli altri”.

53 See Zeller 1880², 35-36 n. 1, 236-238. So also Ioppolo 1980, 24 and 208-216.

54 Hirzel 1877-1883, II 101-102 n. 2.

55 *SVF* 1.565.

56 *SVF* 3.26.

57 *SVF* 3.60.

58 According to Mansfeld/Runia 2020, I, 135, Cleanthes presumably maintained that there were six virtues, “corresponding to the number of parts in which he divided philosophy” (D.L. 7.41 = *SVF* 1.482).

59 On this point, see Dorandi 2005, 50.

adopted by Apollonphanes (and by the Stoics in general, obviously from the Epicurean point of view). As it is especially clear from col. 86 Delattre, Philodemus' aim is precisely to demonstrate (against his Stoic opponent) that, at least in some cases (l. 11: πστ'), the severing of the 'bond of sympathy' between body and soul is painless. Delattre points out that "cette conviction, il la fonde précisément sur le constat qu'il se rencontre des morts indolores (voir *supra*, col. 82,1-6), et loin que les phénomènes s'y opposent, certains confirment indiscutablement cette possibilité".⁶⁰ Thus, although pain accompanies fatal diseases in many cases, it cannot be considered the cause of death in sick people. Pain is rather the result of the close relationship between soul and body, and while death corresponds to the dissolution of that relationship, it will not necessarily be painful.⁶¹ Indeed, in some cases death—that is, the disintegration of the atoms of the soul and the dissolution of its bond with the body—can even be a pleasant experience.⁶²

If this is Philodemus' view, one could hypothesise that, according to Apollonphanes, the moment of death is *always accompanied by pain*. However, we have no way of knowing what strategies he envisioned to cope with this form of pain. In this regard, we can only imagine that those strategies aimed to show that death, despite the physical pain it necessarily entails, *is not an evil*, as Zeno had already argued.⁶³ Therefore, from col. 84 to line 5 of col. 86 of *PHerc.* 1050, Philodemus paraphrased this Stoic view. He then challenged the philosophical foundations of this view, starting from line 6 of col. 86. The direct intervention by Philodemus at this point, with the consequent exposition of the Epicurean point of view on death—which is not to be feared as *it is nothing to us*⁶⁴—and ἀνασθησία,⁶⁵ is proved by the presence of a *diple obelismene* precisely between lines 5 and 6 of col. 86.

60 Delattre 2022, 23 n. 3. On this passage, see also Gigante 1983², 149-151.

61 With regard to this point, I agree with the remarks in Tsouna 2007, 267-269.

62 See Warren 2004, 13 and n. 22, who, in addition to Philodemus' *On Death*, Book 4, also mentions Sen. *De prov.* 6.9, *Ep.* 77.9; Cic. *Tusc.* 1.82; Lucr. 3.172-173.

63 Cf. Sen. *Ep.* 82.9 (= *SVF* 1.196), on the assumption that death is (i.e. can be) glorious, while no evil can be such. It should be noted that this position can also be ascribed to Aristo, although the Seneca passage attesting to it has undergone interpolation (Sen. *Ep.* 94.7 = *SVF* 1.359). On this last point, see Ioppolo 1980, 84-85 and n. 70.

64 Cf., e.g., Epicur. *Ep. ad Men.* 124-127; *RS* II (= *SV* 2); Lucr. 3.830-977. On the Epicurean conception of death in general, see Long 2019, 115-151; concerning Philodemus' case, Tsouna 2007, 239-311.

65 On the Epicurean physiology of death, i.e. physical pain and the relationship between soul and body, cf., e.g., Epicur. *Ep. ad Her.* 63-65 and Lucr. 3.370-829. On this topic, see Warren 2002, who discusses the divergences between Democritus and the Epicureans in relation to the physiology of death, and Percy 2012, who discusses instead the relationship between the concept of ἀνασθησία and the medical debate at the time of Philodemus (as exemplified in particular by Asclepiades of Bithynia).

2.5 Conclusions

From all that has been argued so far, it emerges that Apollophanes is a figure difficult to “label” within the context of first-generation Stoicism. On the basis of the patchy surviving information about him, it is possible to reconstruct a prominent personality on the philosophical level, who with regard to many important points was caught between the extremes of Stoic ‘heterodoxy’ and ‘orthodoxy’. Defining him as a ‘heterodox’ philosopher *tout court* does little justice to the complexity of his positions, especially those which distinguish him from his teacher, sometimes in a striking way. In particular, a) Apollophanes rejected Aristo’s “pan-ethicism” and openly criticised his teacher’s hedonism in his treatise *Aristo*, which—contrary to what one might think—cannot have been a celebratory work; above all, b) he also dealt with certain aspects of dialectic and the Stoic theory of knowledge; and c) he studied Stoic physics, by composing a work, *Physics*, in which he dealt with the topic of vacuum, and developing his own original theory of the soul and its partitions.

I think these elements are enough to conclude that the relations between Apollophanes and Aristo evolved over time and ultimately deteriorated in an irreparable way. Initially Apollophanes was a fervent supporter of his teacher’s theses, but he later distanced himself from him with regard to some fundamental issues, even to the point of openly criticising him for his pro-hedonist tendencies. The treatise *Aristo* most likely sprung precisely from Apollophanes’ need to clarify his own autonomous position and to explain (possibly to the ‘Aristoneans’) the reasons for his dissent. In general, it can be assumed that in the latter phase of his life Apollophanes adopted more ‘orthodox’ views with respect to the genuine Stoic tradition, both in terms of the general approach to philosophical research envisaged by Zeno of Citium, and in terms of the defence of the school’s rigoristic ethical attitude.

3 The Present Edition

The new edition of Apollophanes I am presenting here supplants that by von Arnim both for the number of testimonies, which from five become nine,⁶⁶ and for the citation criterion adopted, which is not limited to lines in which Apollophanes is quoted directly, but extends to the context of each piece of evidence. This citation method allows us, especially in the case of papyrus sources,⁶⁷ to better understand pieces of information covering all the main fields of research into which most Stoics divided philosophy: logic, physics, and ethics.

66 *De facto* they are eight, since T 2 and T 4 coincide.

67 Cf. above all T 9.

The order of the testimonies is thematic: *biographica*, *logica*, *physica*, and *ethica*. Both for the testimonies handed down by manuscripts and for the papyrus sources, the most recent edition is indicated, specifying the corresponding page (or pages) or volume and the critical apparatus. Since in some cases, especially with papyrological pieces of evidence, the critical apparatus has also been established on the basis of previous editions, I have indicated the edition or editions preceding the reference one below the testimony to clarify the *constitutio textus*. In general, I have tried to standardize the critical apparatus as much as possible, but in certain cases the somewhat structurally different criteria followed in the editions of texts transmitted by papyri and codices have led me to slightly vary the editorial criteria for the two types of texts. In particular, the apparatuses of the texts known from medieval manuscripts conform more to the criteria followed by the reference editor. For the Herculaneum papyri, however, I follow my own criteria, which override those adopted by other editors.

Before the critical apparatus, for all testimonies the following items are indicated (when present or necessary): a) the fragments (or *excerpta*) of authors cited directly in the testimony, which are found in other editions or collections; b) the *loci paralleli*, i.e. passages by other authors dealing with the same topic as the testimony (in this case the order that is followed is the chronology of the sources). For the Herculanean testimonies, in addition to the acronyms indicated below, I should point out that the use of *sigma lunatum* is generally avoided. It only appears in cases where the state of conservation of the papyrus does not allow us to determine with certainty whether the letter is part of the beginning, the body, or the end of the word. To avoid the overuse of signs, no *spatia vacua* are reported. Where they have a specific meaning, they are rendered in the text using appropriate punctuation marks. As is always the case in papyrus texts, gaps are marked by sublinear dots included between square brackets; when it is impossible to tell with certainty whether a gap consists of one letter or more, the last dot is printed in round brackets. The letters in bold which are printed in col. 85 Delattre of the testimonies from Book 4 of Philodemus' *On Death* (T 9) indicate a *sottoposto*.⁶⁸ My own conjectures are

68 One of the peculiarities of the Herculaneum papyri is represented by overlapping layers (*sovraposti* and *sottoposti*), that is portions of papyrus layers that remained stuck to the immediately preceding (*sovraposti*) or following (*sottoposti*) winding(s) of a scroll when this was unrolled. Herculanean papyrologists print such layers in bold in their editions, after having restored them to their original position. I have done the same here, whereas Delattre was forced to print *sovraposti* and *sottoposti* in grey in his edition because, as is widely known, the Greek texts of the Collection Budé are all written in bold. Anyway, one may wonder why Delattre chose the colour grey, which seems to be the worst chromatic choice in such a context.

indicated with an asterisk (*). *O* and/or *N* respectively indicate the readings of the Oxford and/or Neapolitan *disegni* of the Herculaneum papyri. An asterisk under a letter (α_{*}β_{*}γ_{*}) means that the editor has changed it as it appears in the *disegni* in the case they are the only sources of the text (*deest P*). With regard to everything else, the Leiden Conventions are followed.

Apollophanis Antiochensis Reliquiae

I. Biographica

De vita activa

T 1.

Phld. *Rhet.* IV, *PHerc.* 463, fr. 13

Ed. Longo 1966, 263.

Fr. 13 (.)] ε καὶ πρὸς τῆς
 ἰδίας] ἐμπνευσθέντες
 γε] φωνῆς, οἱ μὲν ὥσ-
 τε θαυμαστῶς προβή-
 5 ναι] τὴν Ἀπολλοφάνους
 ἐπὶ] τοῦ βήματος τύρ-
 σι]ν ἐζήλωσαν, οἱ δὲ
 καὶ καταπλεύσαντες
 εἰς τὸν λιμένα καὶ παρα-
 10 {φα}σχόντες ἐλπίδας ὡς
 αὐτοὺς “οὐδ’ ἂν τὸ σεμν[ὸν
 πῦρ εἰργάθοι Διὸς / τὸ
 μὴ οὐ κατ’ ἄκρων περ-
 15 λγ_{*}άμων ἐλ_{*}εῖν” τὸν εὐ-
 δ]αίμονα βίον, εἴθ’ ὕστ[ε-
 ρον] ἀντ[εμπ]νευσθέντες
 (.)] τὸ τῆς ἀ[[πο]]<γω>-
 18 [γῆς (.)]
desunt lineae plures

11-14 E. *Ph.* 1175-1176

Fr. 13 (*N*) omnia primum Longo || 1] ε subter lineam vert. apicata sicut τ, υ, ρ, φ (] τε * e.g.) || 9-10 παρα|[[φα]]σχόντες Longo : παρα|φάσχοντες D. Konstan per litteras || 12 inter πῦρ et εἰργάθοι litterae in rasura et spatium vacuum || 13-14 περι[[γ]]άμων ἐ[[λ]]εῖν Longo || 15 βίον (διον *N*) || 18 [[πο]] litterae lineolis supra lineam a librario deletae, αγω- Longo scrips.

*Opera***T 2.**

D.L. 7.140

Ed. Dorandi 2013, 556.⁶⁹

7.140 ἓνα τὸν κόσμον εἶναι καὶ τοῦτον πεπερασμένον, σχῆμα ἔχοντα σφαιροειδές· πρὸς γὰρ τὴν κίνησιν ἀρμοδιώτατον τὸ τοιοῦτο, καθά φησι Ποσειδώνιος ἐν ε΄ τοῦ Φυσικοῦ λόγου καὶ οἱ περὶ Ἀντίπατρον ἐν τοῖς περὶ κόσμου. ἔξωθεν δὲ αὐτοῦ περιεχυμένον εἶναι τὸ κενὸν ἄπειρον, ὅπερ ἀσώματον εἶναι· ἀσώματον δὲ τὸ οἶόν τε κατέχευ⁵σθαι ὑπὸ σωματίων οὐ κατεχόμενον. ἐν δὲ τῷ κόσμῳ μηδὲν εἶναι κενόν, ἀλλ' ἠνώσθαι αὐτόν· τοῦτο γὰρ ἀναγκάζειν τὴν τῶν οὐρανίων πρὸς τὰ ἐπίγεια σύμπνοιαν καὶ συντονίαν. φησὶ δὲ περὶ τοῦ κενοῦ Χρύσιππος μὲν ἐν τῷ Περὶ κενοῦ καὶ ἐν τῇ πρώτῃ τῶν Φυσικῶν τεχνῶν καὶ Ἀπολλοφάνης ἐν τῇ Φυσικῇ καὶ Ἀπολλόδωρος καὶ Ποσειδώνιος ἐν β΄ τοῦ Φυσικοῦ λόγου.

1-3 (κόσμου) Antip. SVF 3.43; Posid. fr. 8 Edelstein/Kidd || 3 (ἔξωθεν)-8 Zen. Cit. SVF 1.95[2]; Chrysipp. SVF 2.543; Apollod. SVF 3.5 || 7 (φησὶ)-8 Posid. fr. 6 Edelstein/Kidd

1 καὶ ἓνα εἶναι κόσμον Suda || τοῦτον om. Φ || 2 ἀρμοδιώτατον P^{pc} (Q) F Φ, Suda : ἀρμονι- B Pa^c. cf. D.L. 1.44 et 2.66 || τὸ τοιοῦτο B¹ P : τὸ τοιοῦτον B² F Φ : τοῦτο Suda || ἐν ε΄ B : ἐν εἰ^ω P (P⁴) : ἐν τῷ πέμπτῳ Cobet || 2 (καθά)-3 (κόσμου) om. Φ || 2 (ἐν)-3 (κόσμου) om. F || 4 τὸ κέντρον εἶναι περιεχυμένον ἄπειρον Suda || ὅπερ] ὡσπερ Suda || εἶναι om. Suda || ἀσώματον² B P F Φ, Suda : κενὸν Zeller 1880³, 181 adn. 3. vd. Goulet (2001) 123 adn. 1 || 4-5 κατέχειν J. Kühn ap. Meibomium || 6 ἀναγκάζει Suda || 6-7 συντονίαν καὶ σύμπνοιαν Suda || 7 φασὶ B || 7 Περὶ <τοῦ> κενοῦ von Arnim || 7 (μὲν)-9 om. F

II. Logica*De sensibus et analogia***T 3.**[Phld. *De sens.*], *PHerc.* 19/698, col. 18AB

Edd. Scott 1885, 253-305: 271 (col. 15), 298 (fr. 11); von Arnim 1903-1905, I, 90; Longo 1966, 267 (*partim*); Monet 1996, 105-106.

Col. 18A χρόνοις, τὴν δ' αἴσθη-
 σιν τὰ καθ' ἓνα κ[ρι]νεῖν
 ἢ μνήμ[η]ς μ[ε]θέξιν,
 Ἀπολλοφάν[η]ς ὑπὸ τοῦ
 5 πιθανοῦ κ[ι]νηθεῖς,
 τὸ μὲν καὶ μνήμην αὐ-

PHerc. 19

69 See Goulet 2001.

ταῖς περιάπτειν κατη-
 δέσθη, τὸ δ' ἀναλογίας
 μετέχειν προσ<ε>δέξα-
 10 θ' ὅπως καὶ τοῦ μηκέ-
 τ' ὄντος ἀποδῶι διαίσι-
 θησιν αὐτῆι [ώ]σπερ, ἵνα
 σώσωμεν ἐναργείαν,
 ἄλλας δέον ἐγβάλλειν
 15 ἐναργείας ἢ διαφέρον-
 τι τήνδε τινὰ ἦν [κ]-
 θαι]ρεῖν ἢ [κ]αθάπερ οὐ
 18 τῶν] ἀναίρου[[ε]]\`μέν'ων
deest linea 1

Col. 18B *deest linea 1* *PHerc. 698*

.]ε[.]ατα[.]εμ[. (.)
]νον[. (.)]ειν
 τόδε μήτε μνή[μης . . . (.)
 . .]εα[. (.)
 5 μετέχειν μετ' ἀναλ[ο-
 γίας μήτ' εἰδούς, ἀλλὰ
 μηδ' ὄναρ οὐκ ἐναργέ[ς
 ὁμοί[ως] ἐστ[ι (.)] καὶ
 9 εν[. .]χον ἄλλως [.]εδε
desunt lineae 2
 12 ἀμ[. (.)
 13 .]α[. (.)
deest linea 1
 14 (.)]θ'
deest linea 1

Col. 18A 8-18 cf. e.g. Epicur. fr. 562 Usener (= [1] 29.10-11 Arrighetti²); *RS XXIII-XXIV*; *Ep. ad Her.* 38, 50-52; *De nat.* XXXIV, *PHerc.* 1431, col. 21 Leone; Phld. *De sign.* III, *PHerc.* 1065, coll. 7, 15 et 22 De Lacy

Col. 18A (*P O N*) 5 κ[ι]νηθείς Monet : θνηθείς Scott : ἀπατηθείς von Arnim : ἡδυνθείς Longo || 3 “καὶ pro ἢ exspectaveris” von Arnim in app. crit. || 9-10 προσ<ε>δέξα[θ'] Longo, acc. Monet : προσ<ε>δέξα[σθ'] Scott : προσ[ε]δέξα[το] von Arnim || 11-12 διαίσιθησιν αὐτῆι Monet : διαίσιθησιν αὐτ[αῖς] von Arnim, acc. Longo : δι' αἰσιθησιν αυτ . . . Scott || 14 ἐγβάλλειν lectio *P O N* : ἐπιβάλλειν von Arnim, qui et ἐκβάλλειν in app. crit. susp. || 15-16 διαφέρον|τι Monet : διαφερόν|τω[ς] Longo || 16-17 Monet || 17 [κ]αθάπερ οὐ Scott || 18 τῶν] * || ἀναίρου[[ε]]\`μέν'ων Monet : ἀνα[ι]ρουσ[μ]ων- Scott || Col. 18B (*P O N*) 1-4 primum Monet || 1 τὰ[ς] ἐμ[πειρίας] * e.g. ||

5-6 ἀναλ[ο]γίας Monet (ἀνα[λο]γίας iam Scott) || 7 μηδ' ὄναρ Monet : μηδ' ΟΛΑΡ(?) Scott ||
7-8 Scott || 9 sqq. ἄλλως Scott, cett. Monet

III. Physica

De vacuo

T 4.

→ T 2.

De anima et eius partitione

T 5.

Aët. 4.4.4-5

Edd. Diels 1879, 390; Mansfeld/Runia 2020, III, 1449.

[*Titulus* δ'. Περὶ μερῶν ψυχῆς (P, S)]

§ 4 οἱ Στωικοὶ ἐξ ὀκτώ μερῶν φασὶ συνεστάναι, πέντε μὲν τῶν αἰσθητικῶν, ὀρατικῶν ἀκουστικῶν ὀσφρητικῶν γευστικῶν ἀπτικῶν, ἕκτου δὲ φωνητικῶν, ἐβδόμου δὲ σπερματικῶν, ὀγδοῦ δ' αὐτοῦ τοῦ ἡγεμονικῶν, ἀφ' οὗ ταῦτα πάντα ἐπιτέταται διὰ τῶν οἰκείων ὀργάνων, προσφερώς ταῖς τοῦ πολῦποδος πλεκτάνας. (P₂, T₄)

§ 5 Ἀπολλοφάνης <ἐξ ἑνῆα μερῶν φησὶ τὴν ψυχὴν συνεστάναι>. (S₁)

§ 4 Chrysipp. *SVF* 2.827 || § 5 cf. Apollon. *SVF* 1.405 (= T 6)

Fontes: P^B: Ps.-Plut. *Plac.* 898E-F; pp. 389^a8-390^a23 Diels ~ P^E: Eus. *Praep. ev.* 15.60, pp. 420.21-421.10 Mras ~ P^Q: Qustā ibn Lūqā, pp. 192-193 Daiber⁷⁰ | S: Stob. 1.49.7a, p. 325.7-8 + 1.50.35, p. 477.18-19 Wachsmuth | T: Theodor. *CAG* 5.19-21, pp. 127.14-128.8 Raeder | cf. Ps.-Iust. *Coh.* 6.2.17-21 Marcovich; Nem. *Nat. hom.* c. 15, p. 72.4-20 Morani | § 4 [1] P^{BQ} : om. P^E || [2] δέ P^E : om. P^{BQ} || [3] δ' P^E, cf. Q : om. P^B || ἐπιτέταται Zeller, prob. Mau et Lachenaud : ἐπιτέταται P^B : τέταται P^E : τέταται Mras : *geordnet werden* Q || [4] προσφερώς—πλεκτάνας P^{BE} : *wie (bei) dem Gewebe der Füße des 'vielfüßig' genannten Lebewesens* Q || § 5 om. P T || [1] ex indice Photiano atque Tert. *De an.* 14.2 (= T 6) suppl. Wachsmuth, Elter sec.

T 6.

Tertull. *De an.* 14

Ed. Waszink 2010, 17-18.⁷¹

14.1. Singularis alioquin et simplex et de suo tota est, non magis instructilis aliunde quam divisibilis ex se, quia nec dissolubilis. si enim structilis et dissolubilis, iam non immortalis. itaque quia non mortalis, neque dissolubilis neque

70 Note that, in the parallel passage of "Arabic Aëtius", only the *doxa* on the Stoics, not that concerning Apollonophanes, is translated. See Daiber 1980, 192-193.

71 See Diels 1879; Philippon 1929 and 1937; Grilli 1957.

divisibilis. nam et dividi dissolvi est et dissolvi mori est. 2. dividitur autem⁵ in partes, nunc in duas a Platone, nunc in tres a Zenone, nunc in quinque ab Aristotele et in sex a Panaetio, in septem a Sorano, etiam in octo penes Chrysippum, etiam in novem penes Apollophanen, sed et in duodecim apud quosdam Stoicorum, et in duas amplius apud Posidonium, qui a duobus exorsus titulis, principali, quod aiunt ἡγεμονικόν, et a rationali, quod aiunt λογικόν,¹⁰ in decem septem exinde prosecuit; ita aliae ex aliis species dividunt animam. 3. huiusmodi autem non tam partes animae habebuntur quam vires et efficaciae et operae, sicut de quibusdam et Aristoteles iudicavit. non enim membra sunt substantiae animalis, sed ingenia, ut motorium, ut actorium, ut cogitatorium, et si qua in hunc modum distinguunt, ut et ipsi illi quinque notissimi sensus,¹⁵ visus auditus gustus tactus odoratus. quibus omnibus etsi certa singulis domicilia in corpore determinaverunt, non idcirco haec quoque distributio animae ad animae sectiones pertinebit, quando ne ipsum quidem corpus ita dividatur in membra, ut isti volunt animam. 4. atquin ex multitudine membrorum unum corpus efficitur, ut concretio sit potius ipsa divisio. specta portentosissimam²⁰ Archimedis munificentiam, organum hydraulicum dico, tot membra, tot partes, tot compagine, tot itinera vocum, tot compendia sonorum, tot commercia modorum, tot acies tibiarum, et una moles erunt omnia. sic et spiritus, qui illic de tormento aquae anhelat, non ideo separabitur in partes, quia per partes administratur, substantia quidem solidus, opera vero divisus. 5. non²⁵ longe hoc exemplum est a Stratone et Aenesidemo et Heraclito; nam et ipsi unitatem animae tuentur, quae in totum corpus diffusa et ubique ipsa, velut flatus in calamo per cavernas, ita per sensualia variis modis emicet, non tam concisa quam dispensata. haec omnia quibus titulis nuncupentur et quibus ex se divisionibus delineantur et quibus in corpore metationibus sequestrentur,³⁰ medici potius cum philosophis considerabunt; nobis pauca convenient.

5-10 Zen. Cit. *SVF* 1.144; Chrysipp. *SVF* 2.874[2]; Panaet. test. 128 Alesse; Posid. fr. 147 Edelstein/Kidd; Sor. *De an.* fr. 10 Podolak. Cf. Aët. 4.4.1-4 Mansfeld/Runia (§ 4 = *SVF* 2.827[1]); Aristot. *De an.* 2.2.413b11-13, 2.3.414a31-32 || 24-30 Strat. fr. 59 Sharples (= fr. 108 Wehrli); Aenesid. B 24 C Polito; Heracl. T 321(b), T 652(a) Mouraviev

1 *instructilis*] in *se structilis* Iunius : *structilis* Kroymann || 2 *et dissolubilis* (*si dissolubilis* iam B Gelenius) || 3 *quia iam non* B Gelenius || 4 *dividetur* A || 5 *Zenone*] Varrone susp. Pamelius, del. Iunius : *in tres* (*scil. a Platone*) <*nunc in quattuor a*> Zenone add. Philippson 1937, 152 adn. 6, prob. Grilli 1957, 72 || 5-6 *in quinque ab Aristotele* Pamelius susp., acc. Diels 1879, 205 et al. : *inquitque* A : *in quinque* B Gelenius : *a filio Nicomachi in quinque* Iunius susp. || 6 et] aut Esser || *panetio* A || *in VII* A : *et in septem* B Gelenius || *in octo*] VIII A || 7 *novem*] VIII A || *apollphanen* A || *duodecim* A B^{ms} : *decem* B Gelenius, acc. Diels 1879, 206 : *duodecim et in quindecim* Reinhardt 1921, 355 adn. 1 || 8 *qui aduobus* A : *quia duobus* B || 9 *tituli* A || *hegemonicon* A || *a rationali*] *irrationali* susp. Stein et Esser || *et irrationali, quod aiunt* ἄλογον ante *et a rationali* per haplographiam intercdisse put. Philippson 1929, 359 || λογικόν] ἄλογον susp. Stein et Esser :

λογικόν in om. A || 10 *decem septem* A] *decem et septem* B Gelenius : *decem* Iunius : *duodecim* Pamelius, acc. Diels 1879, 206 et al. : lectio tradita a Schindler 1934, 59-61 vindicata || *aliae* A : *in alias* B Gelenius || *speties* A || 13 *actorium*] *altorium* susp. La Cerda || 14 *distingunt* A : *distinguuntur* Iunius || *ut del.* Iunius || *in quinque* Gelenius || 14 *novissimi* A || 17-18 *corpus ita dividatur*] *corpussit adividatur* A || 19-20 *portentosissimam* A || 20 *hydrolicum* ed. Rigaltiana tertia || *tot^l*] *toth* A corr. || 21-22 *commertia* A || 25 *est* om. A || *ipsi* A || 26 *defusa* A || 29 *delineantur* D. Konstan per litteras : *detineantur* A B^{mss} : *deriventur* B Gelenius : *distineantur* Kroymann || 30 *cum philosophis*] *tum philosophi* Gelenius

IV. Ethica

De virtute

T 7.

D.L. 7.92

Ed. Dorandi (2013) 528.⁷²

7.92. Παναίτιος μὲν οὖν δύο φησὶν ἀρετάς, θεωρητικὴν καὶ πρακτικὴν· ἄλλοι δὲ λογικὴν καὶ φυσικὴν καὶ ἠθικὴν· τέτταρας δὲ οἱ περὶ Ποσειδώνιον καὶ πλείονας οἱ περὶ Κλεάνθην καὶ Χρύσιππον καὶ Ἀντίπατρον. ὁ μὲν γὰρ Ἀπολλοφάνης μίαν λέγει, τὴν φρόνησιν.

1-4 Panaet. test. 67 Alesse; Posid. fr. 180 Edelstein/Kidd; Cleanth. *SVF* 1.565; Chrysipp. *SVF* 3.261; Antip. *SVF* 3.60

1 οὖν suppl. F^{2mss} || 3 καὶ Ἀντίπατρον suppl. F^{2mss} || μὲν γὰρ] μέντοι M. Patillon ap. Goulet 2001, 93 adn. 7

De voluptate

T 8.

Ath. 7.14.281b-e

Ed. Olson 2021, 383-384.

14.281b. φιλήδονον δ' οἱ ποιηταὶ καὶ τὸν ἀρχαῖόν φασι γενέσθαι Τάνταλον· ὁ γοῦν τῶν Ἀτρειδῶν ποιήσας Κάθοδον ἀφικόμενον αὐτὸν λέγει πρὸς τοὺς θεοὺς καὶ συνδιατρίβοντα ἐξουσίας τυχεῖν παρὰ τοῦ Διὸς αἰτήσασθαι ὅτου ἐπιθυμεῖ· τὸν δὲ πρὸς τὰς ἀπολαύσεις ἀπλήστως διακείμενον ὑπὲρ αὐτῶν τε τούτων μνεῖαν ποιήσασθαι ⁵καὶ τοῦ ζῆν τὸν αὐτὸν τρόπον τοῖς θεοῖς. ἐφ' οἷς ἀγανακτήσαντα τὸν Δία τὴν μὲν εὐχὴν 281c. ἀποτελέσαι διὰ τὴν ὑπόσχεσιν, ὅπως δὲ μηδὲν ἀπολαύη τῶν παρακειμένων ἀλλὰ διατελῆ ταραττόμενος, ὑπὲρ τῆς κεφαλῆς ἐξήρτησεν αὐτῷ πέτρον, δι'

72 See Goulet 2001.

ὄν οὐ δύναται τῶν παρακειμένων τυχεῖν οὐδενός. καὶ τῶν Στωικῶν δέ τινες συνε-
 φήψαντο ταύτης τῆς ἡδονῆς· Ἐρατοσθένης γοῦν ὁ Κυρηναῖος μαθητὴς γενόμενος
 10 Ἀρίστωνος τοῦ Χίου, ὃς ἦν εἷς τῶν ἀπὸ τῆς Στοᾶς, ἐν τῷ ἐπιγραφομένῳ Ἀρίστωνι
 παρεμφαίνει τὸν διδάσκαλον ὡς ὕστερον ὀρμήσαντα ἐπὶ τρυφῇν 281d. λέγων ὧδε·
 “ἦδη δέ ποτε καὶ τοῦτον πεφώρακα τὸν τῆς Ἠδονῆς καὶ Ἀρετῆς μεσότοιχον διορύτ-
 τοντα καὶ ἀναφαινόμενον παρὰ τῇ Ἠδονῇ”. καὶ Ἀπολλοφάνης δὲ (γνώριμος δὲ ἦν καὶ
 οὗτος τοῦ Ἀρίστωνος) ἐν τῷ Ἀρίστωνι, καὶ αὐτὸς οὕτως ἐπιγράψας τὸ σύγγραμμα,
 15 ἐμφανίζει τὴν τοῦ διδασκάλου φιληδονίαν. περὶ δὲ Διονυσίου τοῦ Ἡρακλεώτου
 τί δεῖ καὶ λέγειν; ὃς ἀντικρυς ἀποδύς τὸν τῆς ἀρετῆς χιτῶνα ἀνθινὰ μετημφιάσατο
 καὶ Μεταθέμενος καλούμενος ἔχαιρε, 281e. καίτοι γηραιὸς ἀποστάς τῶν τῆς Στοᾶς
 λόγων καὶ ἐπὶ τὸν Ἐπίκουρον μεταπηδήσας· περὶ οὗ οὐκ ἀχαρίτως ὁ Τίμων ἔφη·

ἦνίκα ἔχρῃν δύνειν, νῦν ἄρχεται ἡδύνεσθαι·

20 ὦρη ἐράν, ὦρη δὲ γαμεῖν, ὦρη δὲ παύεσθαι.

1-3 *Nost.* fr. 4, p. 96 Bernabé || 1-13 *Arist. Ch. SVF* 1.341 (= *Eratost. FGrHist* 241 F 17) || 15-20 *Tim.*
 fr. 17 Di Marco (= *SH* 791) = *Dion. Heracl. SVF* 1.430[1]

6 ἀποτελέσαι A : ἐπιτελέσαι C E : ἐπετέλεσε (structura mutata) Eust. (pp. 1700.63-1701.3 = 1.437.2-6) ||
 11 τὴν ante τρυφῇν praeb. C E || 13 Ἀπολλοφάνης Casaubon : Ἀφάνης A, acc. Olson || 20 παύεσθαι
 A C E Eust. (p. 1691.30-31 = 1.424.38-40) : πεπαύσθαι *Anth. Pal.* et Musurus

De morte

T 9.

Phld. *De mor.* IV, *PHerc.* 1050, coll. 84-86

Edd. Mekler 1885; Bassi 1914, 19-58, 63-73; Kuiper 1925; Gigante 1983², 115-161,
 163-234; Henry 2009, 14-21; Delattre 2022, 20-25.⁷³

Col. 84 .]ον μα[..... *PHerc.* 1050
 .]βαρυν[.....
 ...]μεντ[.....
 ύπνω[.....]δια[.....
 5 δὲ αἰσθητ[ι]κὴν ὕσ[.....
 _σ]τερίσκεσθαι χωρ[ίς τοι]-
 αὐτα μὲν δὴ τατ[..... οἱ περὶ
 τὸν Ἀπολλοφάνην [.....

73 See von Arnim 1888; Pearcy 2012; Delattre 2018, 223-240.

- ἡμῖν δο[κούσι] διαπίπτ[ειν]
 10 Ἐπικούρωι [παρ]ακεχωρ[ηκ] -
 ..]νται δ[.....]ην· α[.....]
 ..]αιδ[.....]με]θα τὸ πο[.....]
 τ[.....] ἀ]πεδείχθη δι[.....]
]ει τις τὸ καὶ με[.....]
 15]ησ[.....]γες καὶ τι[.....]
]υσιν ο[.....]
]ιση[.....]το καιόμε[.....]
] ἀπό[ν]οις [.....]
 20]καν[.....]
deest linea 1
 22]υν[.....]
 23]αι[.....]
deest linea 1
 25]ουγ[.....]
deest linea 1
 27]τα[.....]
 δη[.....] ἱστορημέν[.....]
]ἀγει τὰ μεν[.....]
 30 κα[.....]αττωνω[.....]ιδεν[.....]
]ἀ]πάτην ἐπ[.....]οι[.....]
]ης ψυχῆς γινομενο[.....]
]ο[.....]ι[.....]των δὲ μετα[.....]
]νοις τελευτω[.....]
 35]τον ε[.....]
]ν ἴσχειν τ[.....]
]ἐ]κπνοη[.....]
 38]λησιν[.....]
 Col. 85 *desunt fortasse lineae 27*
 28]τα[.....]
 πη[.....]ο[.....]ητοιμε[.....]
 30 δελα[.....]χωρ]ις πόνου [.....]
]σόμεθα [.....]
 τ[.....] κατὰ μέρος ου[.....]
 ἐκ[.....]ω[.....]εγ· ε[.....]
 ταγε[.....] ἐπιθα[υ]μάζειν [.....]
 35 ο[.....]α[.....]ο]μολογ[.....]
 γε[.....] τὴν α[ίτι]αν τοῦ [.....]

τῆ[ς ψυ]χῆς τεθν[εώ]τες [.]
]ενω[.]
 39]ατον εἶναι [. · συμβή- ||
 Col. 86 σεταί τε κατὰ τὸν λό[γον τούτων μετὰ
 ἄ[κ]ρων ἀλγηδόνων ἐ[πιγίνεσθαι πάσας
 τελευτὰς ἀξιούντων] ἀ]δύν[ατον εἶναι
 τὴν ἀνυπέρβλητον λύεσθαι συ[μπάθει-
 5 αν εἰ μὴ μετ' ὀχλήσεω[ς] ἀνυπερβ[λήτου].

φῆσομέν τε τὴν συμπάθειαν πρ[ὸς τὸ
 σῶμα τῆς ψυχῆς εἰ καὶ τὰ πολλὰ λ[ύεται
 μετ' ὀχλήσεως, αἰτίας [τινὸς] ἢ πυκ[νού-
 σ]ης ἀσυμμέτρως τὰ μ[έρη τ]ῶν ζώ[ιων
 10 ἢ διίστανούσης, ἀλλ' οὐ φ[αμέ]ν γε ἀδ[ύνα-
 τον λυθῆναι ποτ' αὐτὴν [ὀλίγ]ης τυχο[ύ-
 σαν] ἑτεροιώσεως, ἣτις [οὐ]κ ἄρ' [ἔσ]τί τις
 ἀ]λ[γῆ]δος αἰτία. λ[επ]τομερῆς γὰρ
 οὐσ]α καὶ τελῶς εὐκίνητος, ἢ] ψυχὴ κα[ὶ
 15 δι]ὰ τοῦτ' ἐκ μικροτάτ[ων] σ[υν]έστηκεν
 καὶ λει]οτάτων καὶ περιφε[ρε]στά[των],
 καὶ ἐ]σ[παρ]μένη καὶ παρὰ τοῦτο πολλὴν
 ἀ]πορίαν π[αρέχ]ου[σ]ε]· πῶς οὐ[κ] ἐξίπτα-
 20 ται διὰ τῶν πάντ[ων] πόρων ἐν τῇ σαρ-
 κὶ περ]ιεσχημ[ένων]; χ[ἀ]κ τίνος [οὐ]κ ἂν
 εἴπ[οι]με]ν μὴδ' ἀλγηδόν]ο[ς] αἰτία[ν εἶναι
 τῆ]ν τῆς συμπαθείας διά]κρισιν, [οἱ μὴ δε-
 δοίκα]με]ν [αἰσθη]σέσθ' ἔτι γ' ἀ]ποτελεσο-
 25 μέν]ης αὐτῆς;]αμ[. . . .
 συν[.]ώντ[ων, τ]ῶν
 δὲ [. τέ]ρψεως α-
]ακα[. . . .
 τους απ[.] συμβα[ίν]ει
 30 κατα[.]αι περ[ι]χ[α]ροὺς δι' ἄ-
 ωρον [. ὥστ'] ἂν, εἴ τις, ἐπειδήπερ [ἐκ
 τοιούτ]ων συνέστηκε, [ἀ]ξιώη δι[ι-
 αττόντων κατὰ τὴν σύγκρισ]ιν ἀπαύσ-
 τως μεθ' ἡδονῆς γίν[εσθαι] πλείστας τε-
 35 λευτὰς, οὐκ ἂν ἀπίθαν]ον γένοιτο τὸ
 τοῦ]το μὲν συμβαίνε]ν καὶ διὰ τὴν
 ἀνυπέρβλητον κοινω[νίαν] κινήσεως

κα[ι τ]έρψεως· καὶ γὰρ
 . .]όντων μεγα[.
 39 . . .]ολ[.]περ[.

Col. 86 4-5, 17-18 cf. Epicur. *Ep. ad Her.* 48, 50, 52, 54, 63-64; Lucr. 3:376-377, 739-740

Col. 84 (P O N) 5 αἰσθητ[ι]κὴν Mekler || ὑσ[τερ- vel ὑσ[τατ- * || 6 σ]τερίσκεσθαι Mekler || χωρ[ις Gigante, χωρ[ις ἀλγηδόνων coni. Delattre e.g. in app. crit. || 6-7 Mekler || 7 fin. οἱ περὶ] Henry in app. crit. : κατὰ] Gigante || 9 δο[χοῦσι] Henry || διαπίπτ[ειν Gigante || 10 [παρ]αε-χωρ[ηκ- Delattre : [κατ]αεχωρ[ι- Henry || 30 [θ]άττον ω[- (vel [ἐλ]αττόνω[ν] Mekler dub. || ε[ι]δέν[αι Mekler || 31 ἀ]πατήν (sic) Delattre || ἐπ[ι τ]οῖ[ς Delattre dub. in app. crit. : ἐπ[ι]ν[οι]α- * e.g. || 34 ἐν πό]νοισ τελευτῶ[σι Delattre dub. in app. crit. || 36 -]ν ἴσχειν Delattre : συ]νίσχειν Mekler || 37 Delattre, coll. 83,12 et 116,32 conl. || 38 ὄ]λησιν Delattre dub. in app. crit. || Col. 85 (P + subpositum) 29 θν]ητοῖ μέ]ν ὄντες Delattre dub. in app. crit. || 30 χ[ωρ]ις πόνου Delattre in app. crit. || 31 accent. * || 36-37 Delattre || 39 sq. von Arnim 1888 || Col. 86 (P O N) 1 λό[γον Hayter || τούτων μετὰ] Delattre : μετὰ τῶν] Henry : πάσας μετ’] von Arnim 1888 || 2 ἄ[χ]ρων Hayter || ἐπιγίνεσθαι von Arnim 1888 || πάσας] Delattre : τὰς] von Arnim 1888 || 3 ἄξιούντω]ν Hayter, cett. von Arnim 1888 || 4-5 συ[μπά-θει]αν εἰ μὴ Delattre : συ[μπαθίαν] | ἄν μὴ Henry || 7 fin. λ[ύεται Delattre 2018 : γ[ίνεται] Asmis : χ[ί]νισις vel γ[όσος Henry dub. in app. crit. : γ[όσου von Arnim 1888 || 8 [τινὸς Delattre 2018 : [οὔσης] Gigante : [πληγῆ]ς Asmis || 9 μ[έ]ρη Percy 2012 post Mekler : μ[ό]ρια Henry : μ[έ]λη von Arnim 1888 || τῶν ζώ]ων Mekler || 10 φ[αμέ]ν Henry : φ[ασι]ν von Arnim 1888 || 10-11 Henry || 11 [όλιγ]ης Henry : [κούφ]ης Delattre 2018 : [ἄλλ]ης von Arnim 1888 || 12 [οὔ]κ ἄρ’ Henry || [έ]στ[ί] Hayter || 13 λ[επ]τομερῆς (λ[. .]τομερικ O) rest. von Arnim 1888, acc. Delattre 2018 et Delattre : λ[επ]τομερῆς Mekler || 14 οὐ]σ[α Schmidt, cett. Hayter || 15 Hayter || fin. -έστηκ[εν Delattre 2018 post -έστηκ[ε Gigante : -εστηκ[ύ]ια Henry post Mekler || 16 καὶ] H. Diels ap. Vogliano || λει]οτάτων Gomperz || 17 καὶ ἐ]σ[παρ]μένη Delattre : διε]σ[παρ]μένη H. Diels ap. Vogliano || 18 ἀ]πορία]ν Delattre 2018 post Mekler : εὐ]πορία]ν Gigante post Hayter || 19 δι[ιὰ τῶν πάντ]ων Delattre : δι[ιὰ συμμέτρ]ων Tsouna : δι[ιὰ τῶν λεπτ]ῶν Hayter : δι[ιὰ τῶν ἐτοίμ]ων Gigante : λ[επτῶν ὄντ]ων Henry (ὄντ]ων iam Kuiper) || 20 π[ερισχ]ημ[ένων] Delattre : π[λειόν] Henry in app. crit. post π[λέον] von Arnim 1888, deinde ἤ μ[υρίων] Mekler || χ[ά]κ Delattre ex P : ἦ [έ]κ Henry ex O ([έ]κ iam Mekler) || fin. [οὔ]κ ἄν Henry : [δῆ] κἄν von Arnim 1888 || 21 εἴπ[οιμ]ε]ν Delattre : εἴπ[αμ]ε]ν Henry : εἴπ[ωμ]ε]ν von Arnim 1888 || μῆδ’ ἀλγηδόν]ο[ς] Delattre ([ἀλγηδόν]ο[ς] iam Mekler spat. brev.) : τῆς ἀλγηδόν]ο[ς] Delattre 2018 || αἰτία]ν εἶναι von Arnim 1888, acc. Delattre : αἰτία]ς Henry || 22 τῆ]ν von Arnim 1888 || [τῆς συμπαθείας] Delattre ([τῆς συμπαθείας] iam Henry in app. crit.) || διά]χρισιν (]χρισιν O) rest. von Arnim 1888, acc. Delattre || 22-23 [οἱ μὴ δε]ῖδοίκα[με]ν Delattre ([εἰ μὴ κτλ. Delattre [2018]) : [λίαν] von Arnim 1888 || 23 [αἰσθήσεσθ’ ἔ]τι γ’] Delattre : [ἀλγεῖν ταύτης] Delattre 2018 : [ῆς τάχιστ’] von Arnim 1888 spat. brev. || 23-25 Delattre || 26 Mekler || 28 init. τοὺς ἀπ]οσπασμούς Mekler : τοὺς ἄπ]αντας Delattre dub. in app. crit. : τοὺς ἀπ’] αὐτοῦ * e.g. || fin. συμβα[ί]νει Hayter || 29 περ[ι]χ[α]ροὺς Delattre : περ[πέ]ρους Delattre 2018 : κ]ρίπερ [. .]ρους Bassi || 30 ὥστ’] ἄν, εἴ Delattre : φθορ]άν εἴ Delattre 2018 : κ]ἄν εἴ von Arnim 1888 || 30-31 Mekler || 31 [ἀ]ξιώμη Mekler, acc. Delattre : [ἀ]ξιώμη Delattre 2018 ex O || 32 σύ]χρισιν Mekler || 32-33 ἀπαύσ]τως Delattre : οὐ]τως Gigante, H. Diels ap. Vogliano sec., spat. brev. : ὄν]τως Mekler, von Arnim 1888 sec., spat. brev. : πάν]τως Henry spat. brev. || 33 γίν]εσθαι Mekler || [πλειστάς] Delattre : [τάς] Mekler spat. brev. || 34 ἀπ]ίθανον Mekler : ἀπ]ίθανος εἴη (vel sim.) Henry in app. crit. || γένοιτο τὸ] Delattre (2018) : τι λέγοι] ὅτι Tsouna || 35 τοῦ]το μὲν Delattre, post [κατὰ | τοῦ]το von

Arnim 1888 et Delattre 2018 : | [ὁ λέ]γόμεν Henry in app. crit. || συμβαίνει[iv von Arnim 1888 : συμβαίνει[ι Schmidt || [καὶ διὰ] Delattre : [λύεσθαι] von Arnim 1888 : [τυχεῖν] Henry dub. in app. crit. || fin. τῆν] Mekler || 36 κοινω[νίαν von Arnim 1888, acc. Delattre, qui et κοινὸ[τητα dub. in app. crit. prop. || fin. κινήσεως] Delattre, qui et πάλσεως] dub. in app. crit. prop. : παλμοῦ] vel κινήσεως] Delattre 2018 : ἡδονῆς] Henry : μεθ' ἡδονῆς] Tsouna post von Arnim 1888, spat. long. || 37 κα[ι τ]έρψεως Mekler, cett. H. Diels ap. Vogliano || 38 μεγά[λων Delattre in app. crit.

Index fontium

The sources are listed in alphabetical order. Next to each author the relevant testimonies in my edition of Apollonphanes are indicated. The reference edition is provided next to the title of the work. The only manuscripts cited in the *conspectus siglorum* are those that appear in the critical apparatus in relation to the passage pertaining to the single testimony on Apollonphanes.

Aëtius [→ T 5]

[*Compendium de placitis philosophorum*] (edd. Mansfeld/Runia)

P Traditio ps.-Plutarchi

P^B Plutarchi *Epitome*, ed. H. Diels ap. *DG*, 273-444 (cf. etiam Mau 1971 et Lachenaud 1993)

P^E Eusebii *Praeparatio Evangelica*, ed. Mras 1982-1983²

P^Q Ps.-Plutarchi *Placita philosophorum* a Qusṭā ibn Lūqā e lingua Graeca in Arabam translata, ed. Daiber 1980

Q Qusṭā ibn Lūqā

S Traditio Ioannis Stobaei

Stob. 1-2 = ed. Wachsmuth 1884

Stob. 3-4 = ed. Hense 1894-1916

T Theodoreti *Graecarum Affectionum Curatio*, ed. Raeder 1904

Athenaeus Naucratis [→ T 8]

Deipnosophistae (ed. Olson)

A Marcianus gr. Z. 447 (coll. 820) (saec. IX ex.)

C Parisinus suppl. gr. 841 (saec. XV)

E Laurentianus Plut. 60.2 (saec. XIV)

Diogenes Laertius [→ T 2 = T 4; T 7]

Vitae philosophorum (ed. Dorandi 2013)

B Neapolitanus Bourbonicus III B 29 (saec. XII)

F Laurentianus Plut. 69.13 (saec. XIII)

- P Parisinus gr. 1759 (saec. XI-XII)
 Q Parisinus gr. 1758 (saec. XIV *in.*)
 Φ Vaticanus gr. 96 (ff. 29v-88r; saec. XII)

Philodemus Gadarensis

De morte, Liber IV (ed. Delattre 2022) [→ T 9]

- P papyrus Herculaneus 1050
 O apographum Oxoniense
 N apographum Neapolitanum

De rhetorica, Liber IV (ed. Longo 1966) [→ T 1]

- P papyrus Herculaneus 463 (*scorza*)
 N apographum Neapolitanum

[*De sensibus*] (ed. Monet 1996) [→ T 3]

- P papyrus Herculaneus 19/698
 O apographum Oxoniense
 N apographum Neapolitanum

Quintus Septimius Florens Tertullianus [→ T 6]

De anima (ed. Waszink 2010)

- A Agobardus = Parisinus lat. 1622 (saec. IX)
 B editio Martini Mesnartii (Parisiis a. 1545), vulgo Gagneiana

Concordantia editionum

Vassallo	von Arnim
T 1	<i>deest</i>
T 2	SVF 1.404
T 3	SVF 1.407 (<i>partim</i>)
T 4 = T 2	SVF 1.404
T 5	<i>deest</i>
T 6	SVF 1.405
T 7	SVF 1.406
T 8	SVF 1.408
T 9	<i>deest</i>

von Arnim	Vassallo
SVF 1.404	T 2 = T 4
SVF 1.405	T 6
SVF 1.406	T 7
SVF 1.407	T 3
SVF 1.408	T 8

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